

Germany

3rd wave survey - 2023

Age groups

Data collection was carried out in **6 schools** and involved **984 students**.

Gender distribution

Financial situation of the family

4 Dimensions of Digital Skills

On average, adolescents reported **being skilled** in 62% of the digital **communication and interaction activities**, but only in 38% of the activities related to **information and navigation**.

Self-reported performance on skills increases slightly with age for all dimensions of digital skills.

On average, boys reported being skilled in 60% of **technological and operational activities** compared to girls who reported 49%.

Knowledge items*

The average of correct answers of the **digital knowledge questions** is 55%. The percentage of correct answers is similar between boys and girls and increases with age.

* Respondents answered a set of questions designed to measure their actual knowledge about how the internet and digital technologies work.

How digital literacy *has increased* among adolescents participating in all three waves (N = 403)

In 2023, the **communication and interaction** dimension had the highest level of digital literacy (61% of the skills and knowledge items). The lowest level (49%) was found for the **information and navigation** dimension which, however, increased most (7%) from 2021 to 2023.

Communication and interaction skills

Content creation and production skills

Information and navigation skills

Digital literacy* is a combination of digital skills and knowledge regarding how the internet and digital technologies work.

*The levels of digital literacy are a merger of self-reported high-level skills and the correct answer on the knowledge items. For technological and operational skills digital literacy could not be accounted for due to a lack of knowledge items.

In 2022 and 2023, the 16- to 17-year olds had the highest levels of digital literacy. In all waves, boys have higher levels of digital literacy (2023: 56%) in comparison to girls (2023: 50%). The results of the third survey wave show that boys and girls have similar levels for digital knowledge items (B: 57%, G: 59%), but girls report less digital skills at a high level (B: 56%, G: 51%).

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